

INTERACTION OF CARBON MONOXIDE AND HYDROGEN UNDER
SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE: PRODUCTION OF FORMAL-
DEHYDE. PART III. INFLUENCE OF CATALYSTS AND
OTHER FACTORS

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Influences of wall catalysts; inter-electrode distance, surface-volume ratio and frequencies of the exciting potentials have been investigated on carbon monoxide-hydrogen interaction leading to formaldehyde formation. It has been found in agreement with the homogeneous nature of the reaction that surface catalysts have little influence on the change, while increasing volume of the discharge space is conducive to increased reaction.

Results of the investigation of the influence of temperature and certain other factors (as gas composition, applied potential and rate of flow etc.) on the production of formaldehyde by the interaction of carbon monoxide and hydrogen under silent discharge have been already reported (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 366; 1950, 31A, 317). The present communication records an extension of these studies with respect to the following factors: (i) catalysis, (ii) inter-electrode distance, (iii) surface-volume ratio and (iv) supply frequency.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The general arrangement of the apparatus and the electrical circuit were the same as in earlier experiments (*loc. cit.*). About 3000 c.c. of the gas mixture ($\text{CO}:\text{H}_2 = 1:1$ by volume) was circulated at the rate of 5 litres per minute through the ozoniser excited by an A.C. supply of the desired frequency (500 and 50 cycles) at potentials a few hundred volts above the appropriate threshold. The effluent gas before being returned to the gas holder was passed through three wash traps connected in series to wash it off the soluble products. Duration of each experiment was six hours' exposure to discharge, at the cessation of which liquors from wash traps were estimated for formaldehyde and acid; the residual gas was measured and analysed with an Orsat's apparatus with the usual absorbents for CO , CO_2 and unsaturated hydrocarbons.

In experiments with catalysts a ground-in-glass type ozoniser, excited by 4.68 kV of 500 cycles A.C., was used. A nearly uniform coating of the catalyst (*vide infra*) under investigation was given on the electrode surface. The results are presented in Table I.

Influence of the inter-electrode distance of the ozoniser was studied with 3 ozonisers, each of effective length 265 mm. and inter-electrode distance 1.162, 3.305 and 4.15 mm. respectively. In each case the ozoniser was excited by 500 cycles A. C. potentials, about 0.8 kV. higher than the appropriate threshold value. Results are summarised in Table II.

TABLE I

Influence of catalysts.

Applied potential = 4.68 kV. Rate of circulation = 5 litres/min.

No.	Catalyst.*	Gas mixture circulated.	Gas mix. consumed (e.c.)†	CO consumed.	H ₂ CHO.	Analysis of the residual gas					
						HCHO in terms of conversion.	Acidity (N/25-NaOH)	CO ₂ .	Unsat. hydrocarbons.	CO.	H ₂ + sat. hydrocarbons.
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10.	11	12
1.	CuO+MnO ₂ +Co ₃ O ₄	2963c.c.	693 (23.4)	547 c.c.	0.08060 g.	12.6%	4.1c.c.	4.7%	3.5%	41.2%	50.6%
2.	CuO+MnO ₂	3004	993 (33.1)	615	0.07502	10.5	15.2	6.0	3.6	44.1	46.3
3.	Ni ₂ O ₃ +Al ₂ O ₃	2964	387 (13.1)	306	0.07551	21.4	16.1	2.6	1.8	45.6	50.0
4.	Fine copper wire wound on the inner electrode	2920	529 (17.9)	470	0.07307	13.7	13.8	4.9	2.4	41.5	51.2
5.	Finely divided Cu powder+Cr ₂ O ₃	2900	520 (17.9)	405	0.08923	19.4	11.2	2.5	3.7	43.9	50.0
6.	Copper chromite Cu (CrO ₃) ₂	2968	525 (17.7)	502	0.08632	15.2	9.9	4.2	2.0	40.2	53.6
7.	CuO+MgO+Co ₃ O ₄ +KHCO ₃	2982	562 (18.9)	450	0.07183	13.8	0.0	3.5	1.2	43.0	52.3
8.	Ni ₂ O ₃ +MoO ₃	2937	482 (16.4)	438	0.07894	15.7	11.6	3.5	2.3	41.9	52.3
9.	Glass wool	2988	1312 (33.9)	876	0.07979	7.9	24.9	9.6	3.6	31.3	55.5
10.	Ni ₂ O ₃ +Cr ₂ O ₃	2900	500 (17.2)	461	0.09311	17.7	3.9	3.5	2.4	41.2	52.9
11.	Ni ₂ O ₃ +CeO ₂	2945	485 (16.5)	410	0.07773	16.4	3.2	3.7	2.5	43.2	50.6
12.	Nil	2954	989 (33.5)	724	0.07803	9.4	30.7	7.4	4.9	38.3	49.4
13.	Nickel powder +MgO	2991	678 (22.7)	571	0.07881	12.2	6.0	4.5	3.0	40.0	52.5
14.	Ni ₂ O ₃ +ThO ₂	2937	450 (15.3)	395	0.08982	19.8	2.5	2.5	3.0	43.2	51.3

* Two main catalysts, viz. copper oxide and nickel oxide, have been used. The oxides of other substances stated have been used as promoters in about decimolar proportion of the main catalyst.

† The figures in parenthesis in column 4 refer to percentage.

TABLE II

Influence of inter-electrode distance.

Rate of circulation = 5 liters/min. Temperature = 29°.

No.	Inter-electrode distance.	Applied potential (kV).	Surface (sq. mm.) volume (c.mm.)	Gas mixture circulated.	Yield of formaldehyde			Analysis of the residual gas				
					Gas used up c.c.	(N/20-NH ₄ CNS).		Acidity (N/25-NaOH)	CO ₂ .	Unsat. hydrocarbon.	CO.	H ₂ +sat. hydrocarbon.
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1.	1.1625mm.	8.4	$\frac{26570}{15440}$	2927c.c.	628 (21.5)	76.5c.c.	0.1148g.	40.3c.c.	5.0%	3.7%	43.2%	48.1%
2.	3.305	10.2	$\frac{22994}{37980}$	2900	716 (24.7)	81.4	0.1221	32.2	4.8	2.4	41.7	51.1
3.	4.15	10.5	$\frac{21581}{44770}$	2936	881 (30.0)	84.4	0.1266	31.5	3.0	1.8	40.8	53.5

TABLE III

Influence of supply frequency.

Rate of circulation = 5 litres/min.

No.	A. C. cycles.	Applied potential (kV).	Gas mixture circulated.	Gas used up	Formaldehyde	Acidity (N/25-NaOH)	Analysis of the residual gas				
							CO ₂ .	Unsat. hydrocarbon.	CO.	H ₂ +sat. hydrocarbon.	
	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
1.	50	6.92	2950 c.c.	121 c.c. (4.1)	0.01810 g.	3.7 c.c.	2.56%	2.56%	47.45%	47.45%	
2.	50	8.24	2909	164 (5.64)	0.02874	6.2	2.35	2.35	45.87	49.43	

Figures in parenthesis in column 5 in Tables II and III refer to percentage.

Surface area and volume of the annular space of these ozonisers have been calculated and shown in column 4, Table II. Bearing of these factors on formaldehyde formation has been discussed with reference to similar earlier experiments.

Influence of supply frequency has been investigated with respect to 500 and 50 cycles of A. C. The results are summarised in Table III.

D I S C U S S I O N

As will be seen from Table I, column 6, the yield of formaldehyde in the various experiments using different catalysts (column 2) is very nearly a constant quantity, viz. on an average about 0.0806 g. The mean variation from this is of the order of $\pm 6.5\%$. The quantities of the total gas mixture and carbon monoxide consumed (columns 4 & 5) on the other hand show a wide variation: in the case of former 387 c.c. to 1012 c.c. and in the latter, 306 to 876 c.c. Formation of acid (column 8) varies widely: in terms of $N/25$ -NaOH it varies from 0.0 c.c. to 30.7 c.c. It does not appear to be directly connected with the formaldehyde yield, but seems to be related with the total amount of the gas mixture and carbon monoxide consumed (columns 4 & 5). For example, in experiments 2, 9 and 12, where acid is formed to a great extent, viz., 15.2, 24.9 and 30.7 c.c. ($N/25$ -NaOH), the quantity of gas mixture and CO consumed are 993 and 615; 1012 and 876; 989 and 724 c.c. respectively, the average consumption of these being 629 and 512 c.c. There does not appear to be any simple relationship between the yield of formaldehyde (column 6) and either the yield of unsaturated compounds, the acid or the CO_2 formed (columns 10, 8 & 9). On the consideration of these facts it is concluded therefore that the reaction giving rise to formaldehyde is not affected by the surface catalysts employed, a conclusion which is in agreement with the earlier finding (*loc. cit.*), viz., the reaction,

which is the primary reaction giving formaldehyde, is a homogeneous one. The results further suggest that most probably formaldehyde is not an intermediate stage in the formation of CO_2 and/or acid or unsaturated compounds, because, although the quantities of these formed are exceedingly large in experiments 2, 9 and 12, the yield of HCHO is constant, within 2 to 6 % of the average. It is difficult to visualise the role of various catalysts in the formation of these substances, but the results of experiment 9 with glass wool, where the active surface for nearly the same volume of the discharge space is very large, are suggestive of their formation by surface reactions. This would appear to receive additional support from the experiments in Table II.

The earlier results, where ozonisers made out of the same glass tubings but of different length were used (Part I, *loc. cit.*, p. 372), have shown that with the increasing length of the ozonisers the volume of gas mixture consumed increases although the formaldehyde yield shows a decline. In these experiments the surface-volume ratio and the inter-electrode distance remained constant. The increased consumption of gases is therefore evidently due to longer time of contact of the gases inside the ozoniser.

In the present experiments, summarised in Table II, the length of the ozoniser has been kept constant and the diameter of the inner and outer electrode varied resulting in an altered inter-electrode distance and surface-volume relationship (vide columns 2 and 4). The increasing inter-electrode distance in the three tubes (1.16, 3.31 and 4.15 mm.) has necessitated the application of higher applied potentials (8.4, 10.2 & 10.5 kV) which are in all cases about 500 volts higher than the appropriate threshold values. The yield of formaldehyde (column 8) is nearly a constant quantity, though a slightly increasing trend is perceptible with increasing inter-electrode distance and volume of the discharge space (columns 2 and 4). The volume of gas consumed has also increased from 628 to 881 c.c. (column 6).

According to Joshi (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, 25, 127, 140; *Curr. Sci.*, 1939, 8, 548), in an ozoniser reaction the absolute values of applied potentials are of little significance; it is only the value $V - V_m$ (where V is the applied potential and V_m the threshold) that affects the energy available for excitation. Since in the present experiments applied potentials have been adjusted to give very nearly a constant $V - V_m$, the electrical conditions in the discharge tube might be assumed, in all cases, to be very nearly similar. Therefore, the increased consumption of gases (vide column 6) cannot be attributed to the increasing applied potentials (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*, p. 373) and must be due to increased reaction owing to the increased volume of the discharge space (vide column 4). It has been suggested earlier (*loc. cit.*) that the formation of formaldehyde takes place by a homogeneous process. Since the volume of the discharge space has increased in these experiments, an increase in the formaldehyde yield is also expected. As seen from column 8, this is so, though, of course, this augmented yield of formaldehyde does not show a quantitative correspondence with the increase in volume of the discharge space.

A consideration of the composition of the residual gas with respect to CO (Table II, column 12) and H₂ plus saturated hydrocarbons formed (column 13) suggests that with increasing volume of the discharge space there has been an augmented formation of the saturated hydrocarbons. This fact considered with the increased consumption of gases (column 6) suggests that besides the formaldehyde formation there are other homogeneous reactions which result in the formation of saturated hydrocarbons, and possibly water. What can be a possible mechanism of such a reaction is under investigation.

It is interesting to observe that although the overall reaction, as indicated by the volume of gas consumed (column 6), the yield of formaldehyde (column 8) and that of saturated hydrocarbons (column 13) have increased with the increasing discharge space (column 4), the quantities of acid, CO₂ and unsaturated hydrocarbons formed (columns 9, 10 and 11 respectively) show a gradual and definite decline. Figures representing the electrode surface area and volume of the discharge space (column 4) indicate that the absolute value of the former has decreased in the three ozonisers from 26570 sq. mm. to 21581 sq. mm. It has been suggested (*vide supra*) that the formation of the last mentioned three substances is catalysed by the active surface, a view that receives confirmation from the results under discussion where the relationship between the surface area and the yields of these is found to be linear.

Influence of supply frequency is evident from Table III, where the results of two typical experiments—one at 8.24 kV and other at 6.92 kV of 50 cycles—are presented. The yields of formaldehyde (column 6) as well as the volumes of the gas mixture consumed (column 5) are very low when compared to experiments with 500 cycles in Tables II and I. The influence of increased applied potential at 50 cycles also is similar to that with 500 cycles (vide Part I, *loc. cit.*, p. 373), viz., an increased overall reaction as indicated by increased consumption of gases, increased acid and hydrocarbon formation (vide columns 5, 7 and 11).

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